

Joint Response to the Genesis Mission RFI from the Alliance for Data Science and AI (ADSA) and the United States Research Software Engineer Association (US-RSE)

The [Alliance for Data Science and AI](#) is a professional association advancing responsible data science and AI across all fields of academic research, education, and training. **Contact: Micaela Parker, Founder and Executive Director, micaela@alliance4datascience.ai**

The [United States Research Software Engineer Association \(US-RSE\)](#) is a national professional organization and community-driven association advancing the recognition, professionalization, and impact of Research Software Engineers across academia, National Laboratories, and industry. **Contact: Sandra Gesing, Executive Director, sandra@us-rse.org**

Co-authors: Steve Van Tuyl, Nathaniel J. Robinson, and Michael J. Mykins, Alliance for Data Science and AI; Elaine M. Raybourn, University of Central Florida

Executive Summary

AI may be the most transformative technology of this generation, potentially enabling significant acceleration of scientific discovery and societal benefits at a scale far beyond what humans alone can achieve. The Genesis Mission's ambition to train 100,000 scientists and engineers in AI over the next decade through coordinated initiatives that treat AI technology and competency as foundational is commendable. The workforce demands of a scalable AI-powered innovation ecosystem will encompass the full lifecycle of AI development and implementation, as well as application by domain-specific practitioners seeking to amplify their work with AI tools. As stewards and operators of the building blocks of a robust AI ecosystem, and **as educators of an emerging AI-enabled scientific workforce, Data Scientists (DSs) and Research Software Engineers (RSEs) in academia are key drivers in achieving this ambitious goal, acting as essential workforce multipliers who operationalize AI into sustained scientific infrastructure.** ADSA and US-RSE are providing this Response to ensure dedicated investment in the strong and ongoing partnerships between our organizations, Federal decision-makers, and the sectors in which much of this emerging workforce will eventually operate. Importantly, our organizations represent institutional and individual members from academia, industry, and National Laboratories, positioning us as strategic enablers of the dual-competency education and training envisioned by the Mission.

In responding to the individual questions listed below, we wish to emphasize three cross-cutting points regarding the education and training components of the Genesis Mission:

- **AI's impacts are society-level, and AI education and training should reflect this.** The Genesis Mission and the educational programs and resources it supports must be designed intentionally to benefit all of society. Long term, AI could power an accelerated R&D enterprise that yields extraordinary abundance, but it could also intensify inequality and economic stratification if access and benefits become concentrated. The Mission should explicitly distribute capacity across geographies, institution types, and economic resource levels.
- **Utilize cross-sectoral collaboration to advance education and training.** By fortifying partnerships between academic institutions, industry, and National Laboratories, the Genesis Mission can leverage the expertise of DSs and RSEs in both education and training to equip

trainees with the interdisciplinary knowledge and practical skills needed to bridge AI and other scientific and engineering disciplines.

- **Dual competency is necessary but not sufficient.** We recommend a third competency: the skills and practice required to work effectively as a *human-AI team*. Scientists need to know when an AI output is reliable, when and how to override it, and how to maintain independent judgment when AI-generated solutions are fluent and confident but inaccurate, or, in the worst case, potentially harmful. The Mission should support training around accuracy and transparency, privacy and security, scientific integrity, and ethical use to ensure scientists who operate AI tools recognize when those tools fail or pose unacceptable risk.

Through resource provision, partnership building, real-world learning, and targeted mentorship across all education levels, the Genesis Mission can leverage the expertise and experience of Data Scientists and Research Software Engineers to systematize these principles in scientific training and practice, advancing the Mission’s vision of a productive AI-enabled R&D workforce that serves as the backbone of a vibrant discovery-driven economy.

Responses to Individual Questions

1. *How can DOE catalyze research collaborations between DOE National Laboratories, universities, and industry to meet the goals of the Genesis program?*

By providing access to its unique cadre of enabling resources and clear pathways for impact that reach students across diverse academic settings. This includes:

- **Resource enablement (infrastructure and training):** offer funding and enable access to high-performance computing/specialized compute resources that most universities and research groups don’t have locally. Access to infrastructure must be paired with access to training that is available to and appropriate for a breadth of domain applications and educational institutions.
- **Operational partnerships:** leverage existing federal grand challenge mechanisms (moonshots, prize challenges, hackathons) to focus and support collaborations among universities, industry, and National Labs on well-defined scopes and deliverables, particularly those with high impact for scientific discovery, national security, and energy innovation.
- **Targeted training opportunities across institution types:** because ~40% of all undergraduates are enrolled at community colleges, provide internship opportunities at DOE National Labs and other DOE research facilities in a clearly defined partnership arrangement for community college students.

2. *How can DOE incentivize partnerships between universities, DOE National Laboratories, industry, and philanthropic organizations to 1) establish new training paths for bachelor’s and master’s degrees focused on dual competencies in AI and scientific/engineering disciplines and 2) provide innovative experiences to prepare doctoral students and post-doctoral associates for careers in AI for science?*

- **Competency integration, not co-existence:** DOE-led partnerships should support research and educational experiences where AI is embedded in scientific practice, not appended as a parallel component. This change in curriculum design will not be simple, and will require resources to support faculty and other instructors.
- **Cross-sector competency frameworks:** fund cross-sector consortia that jointly define what “dual competency” means in practice and outline competency profiles for AI-for-science roles at all degree levels. Competency profiles offer concrete targets for program development and provide employers with a shared vocabulary for describing hiring needs.
- **Co-designed curricula and experiences:** build degree programs around the competency definitions and profiles that incorporate cross-disciplinary experiences involving hands-on contributions to high-impact projects.

- **Clear career pathways and mentorship:** partnerships should include mentorship and visibility into what the job looks like at National Labs, in academia and industry, so training aligns with fundamental roles. ADSA members have more than a decade of experience in dual-mentored doctoral and postdoctoral training programs, while US-RSE is building mentorship programs to foster professional development in scientific domains that require research software.
- **Tool access as infrastructure:** provide funding or other mechanisms to ensure students and researchers have reliable access to high-capability AI tools (not just free tiers).

3. *What attributes might attract undergraduates to programs that offer dual competency degrees?*

Programs that are financially accessible, have clear connections to meaningful career paths, and connect AI skills to solutions for real-world problems will attract undergraduates. Programs that endow students with highly transferable skills and frame AI competency as a source of professional agency (learning to direct and evaluate AI rather than compete with it) will attract students who might otherwise avoid STEM fields out of concern that "AI will take my job." The message should be that these programs prepare researchers who know how to appropriately deploy AI tools, evaluate them for bias and error, and explain their use to stakeholders.

4. *Beyond funding, what other opportunities could DOE, including its National Laboratories and user facilities, bring to these partnerships?*

DOE can leverage its vast network of labs, facilities, and experts to provide resource access and opportunities for mentorship, engagement, and professional development across two- and four-year academic institutions. These opportunities can take a number of forms and may include compute and facilities access at DOE labs, access to specialized data, facilitated mentorship programs, curriculum co-design (with academia, DOE researchers, and industry partners), or professional development opportunities for university faculty and staff across a range of domain and topic areas.

5. *In addition to classroom and research training, what other contributions could universities make to support these partnerships?*

Universities can serve a multifaceted role as enablers, coordinators, and mutual beneficiaries of partnerships that translate dual-competency education and training into real-world impact. These facets include:

- **Talent identification:** university faculty are uniquely poised to identify strong talent among their students. Faculty could connect top students to internship, apprenticeship, and post-graduation employment opportunities in industry and National Labs. University partners could administer a "rising stars" program for promising dual competency-trained students.
- **Stackable real-world training:** Academia can administer career exploration programs involving rotations, internships, and apprenticeships with National Labs and the private sector. Analogous to medical residencies, programs can translate classroom and research training into real-world roles with increasing independence and problem complexity.
- **Bidirectional resource sharing:** universities can similarly share their unique resources (e.g., data assets, subject matter expertise) with partners in industry and National Labs, creating a virtuous cycle of collaboration built on shared digital and human resources.
- **Translational deliverables:** Universities can enable industry-sponsored research, patenting and tech transfer, small business grants, and venture creation and incubation.
- **Scaffolded mentorship:** beyond traditional one-on-one mentoring, the Mission can support mentorship that allows students to learn end-to-end R&D workflows from experts at each stage of the pipeline. Universities can make essential contributions by engaging mentors across academic departments and research centers and their alumni networks.

- **Professional socialization:** universities can serve a central role in developing “soft skills” for the future workforce. The importance of these skills will only grow as AI’s ability to convey “hard” knowledge continues to burgeon in educational settings.

6. *Beyond funding, what types of contributions could industry and philanthropic organizations make to enhance these partnerships and enrich the experiences of the students?*

Industry and philanthropic organizations can add value by contributing sector-specific expertise and mentorship, and by furnishing projects grounded in authentic, real-world contexts that allow students to reap tangible benefits beyond the knowledge and skills they gain. These organizations can ensure:

- **Tangible value to students:** companies and organizations can ensure that students who participate in experiential learning realize direct, tangible benefits, such as compensation for work performed, preservation of intellectual property rights, and the ability to share their portfolio of work with future employers by prioritizing projects whose details and outputs can be disclosed.
- **Real-world project exposure:** companies and organizations can furnish projects with the potential for real impact and, conversely, that are impacted by real-world constraints (security, reliability, maintainability, deployment), helping students learn beyond contrived prototypes in the classroom.
- **Career visibility and targeted mentorship:** help students understand the landscape of roles at the AI–science intersection and offer sector-specific mentorship for students committed to, or with interest in, exploring industry and philanthropic careers.
- **Professional development for educators:** provide faculty with opportunities and training to build sector-specific knowledge and skills they can then integrate into their pedagogy and curricula.

7. *In addition to AI, which scientific and engineering disciplines are well-suited for this dual competency training approach?*

Although STEM disciplines are a natural fit for AI dual competency training, the Mission should take a broad view to encompass any discipline in which (a) AI tools are powerful but require domain judgment to apply correctly, and (b) mathematical foundations provide the basis for understanding what AI systems are doing. The common thread should be disciplines where AI augments human reasoning rather than replacing it, and where the consequences of uncritical AI use are significant. Generally, dual competency would be most impactful in disciplines that are data-rich, computationally intensive, or operationally time-sensitive, where AI can accelerate discovery workflows, literature synthesis, software/tool development, and analysis pipelines. Due to AI’s disruptive potential, the suitability of existing disciplines for AI integration may change over time, and new domains may emerge as AI capabilities expand. Educators must be equipped with the resources needed to maintain agility and responsiveness as science and engineering evolve for the foreseeable future.

8. *What components are needed for an effective dual competency degree program to best prepare students for successful careers at the bachelor’s level? At the master’s level?*

At both levels, the core of such a program would be a strong foundation in a scientific domain, plus AI fundamentals (theory and practice), brought together in an integrated curriculum that provides ample opportunities to apply both sets of competencies simultaneously to solve real problems. These programs should incorporate a pedagogical approach that teaches students to use AI as a collaborative reasoning tool while maintaining accountability for the quality and correctness of their work. This means teaching students to articulate their reasoning to AI systems, to cultivate reasonable skepticism about AI outputs, and to demonstrate core competencies independent of AI assistance. Key components for bachelor’s and master’s programs are detailed in our long-form response, [available here](#).

9. *What components are needed to prepare graduate students and post-doctoral students for successful careers at the nexus of AI and science?*

Training should focus on **how to use AI-assisted research workflows** for unambiguous tasks that accelerate workflows, such as literature review, code development, and rapid software prototyping; and, developing rigorous verification habits, such as grounding models, verifying sources, verifying code outputs, and ensuring that speed does not come at the cost of accuracy. Developing exploratory data analysis skills and learning to critically evaluate how the inputs (the data) are affecting the outputs of AI models, and **professional software engineering standards and practices** focused on understanding unit testing, security, maintainability, reproducibility, and scientific integrity, are essential for building trustworthy AI-enabled scientific systems.

In parallel, training should also set clear **guidance and expectations for the ethical use of AI in science**, focused on: how not to use AI (generating publications, spreading deception or misinformation, laundering unverified claims into the literature, etc.); how to identify societal stakes and risks that may come from specific AI use cases; the context of the scientific domain in which the AI is being applied, because the “societal stakes” and misuse risks are often domain-specific. Training should also focus on how to **spot risk, escalate or seek review, and document choices**.

10. *How could partnerships between DOE, universities, and industry provide new training opportunities for students to best prepare them for private and public sector jobs?*

Programs should expose trainees to the norms, constraints, and opportunities of non-academic sectors rather than solely train them for the academic pipeline. Partnerships can create new training opportunities that prepare students for both private- and public-sector jobs by giving them authentic, mentored work experience under real constraints, such as joint projects that mimic real-world workflows (including security and quality expectations). Students should be paired with a practicing mentor in the private or public sector so they understand how work is executed and reviewed, all while gaining hands-on experience in directly relevant tooling and computing environments and understanding the expectations of that career.

11. *What type of experiential opportunities are needed to complement classroom instruction to best prepare students for future jobs?*

Students should engage in various complementary types of experiential learning at different stages of their education and training. Specific examples include: **Shadowing and mentorship** with practicing researchers/engineers, including those at National Labs and in industry; **Project-based collaborations, including paid internships** in which students make hands-on contributions to authentic research applications; **Externships for faculty** to bring back real-world knowledge and skills that will benefit their students in the classroom. An equally valuable experiential resource for mastering AI competency would be **structured learning tools focused on AI-augmented scientific reasoning** for active learning. The difference matters: an AI tutor optimizes for answer delivery, while a **thought partner optimizes for students’ capacity to reason independently** in conditions that mirror actual scientific practice.

13. *How could community colleges and other educational institutions contribute and be included in this pipeline?*

ADSA and US-RSE can serve the Mission in this capacity by identifying specific AI infrastructure needs and brokering partnerships between community colleges and resource-rich institutions that focus on AI infrastructure sharing, foundational AI literacy, and applied AI fellowships that are specifically designed for students from community colleges.